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CURRICULUM TRANSACTION THROUGH THEATER METHOD -THEORY AND PRACTICE

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1.THEORY

The basic principle of all performing arts is instruction. They teach, they transact a concept to the spectators. Both the eastern and Western dramatists had made this point clear. Bharata, the Indian aesthete had stated that,

“I shall make a fifth veda on the Natya with the semi historical tales (itihasa) which will conduce to duty (dharma), wealth (artha) as well as fame will contain good counsel and collection [of other materials for human well being],will give guidance to people of future as well in all their actions, will be enriched by the teaching of all scriptures (sastra) and will give a review of all arts and crafts (silpa).”

(*The Natyasastra*, p 90-91)

The objectives of drama as observed by Bharata, as enhancing the wisdom through instructions and that of Aristotle as knowledge provider, when analysed from the educational point of view can be seen as similar to the objectives of curriculum. That means the ultimate aim of both drama and curriculum are not two but one and the same. This makes it very clear that Drama can be used as an effective tool for the transaction of curriculum in the classroom.

It was Bertolt Brecht, the German dramatist who proved the revolutionary roles a drama can play by providing a theoretical base to it. When the stage was used as a medium to awake the exploited Latin Americans against the colonial and imperialist powers, the result was “Theater of the oppressed”. “Theater of the oppressed” was the product of the union of Augusto Boal and Paulo Faer who opined that theater is the most powerful weapon for the struggle for freedom. The role of drama in knowledge construction was made explicit by Brecht by elevating his oppressed spectators into observers and learners through his theater of experiments which was no way different from the pedagogy of teaching. That means knowledge is not meant for transferring but it should be constructed. And this is the basic principle of modern curriculum too.

G. Sankaranpillai in his article, *University Theater*, points out, “If popular plays which are part of curriculum of various courses are included in the campus theater, it can serve an educational purpose also. This may sound like an utopian dream as it is not tested in India. But many of the European Universities have been effectively practicing it”. GS was hinting at the use of theater for learning popular plays included in the Syllabus. But this is just one of the objectives of theater learning. Rather, this paper is about the effective use of theater in learning any topic or subjects.

In 2008 Mexican State University has used Theater method for the management studies of the UG students. In 2008 University of Sweden had introduced a simulation programme of three day drama training under the title ‘Marathon Death Exercise’ for the medical students. To report the death news or to inform the fatal condition of the patient to the relatives is the most challenging situation for the doctors. Marathon Death Exercise was introduced in the curriculum in order to equip the medical students to handle this critical situation smoothly. This training was based on the concept of Forum Theater of Augusto Boal. The behavior of the medical students was video recorded and also their body language, tone and dialogue rendering were critically analysed. After which the students were given rehearsal to improve their defective areas whereby providing skills and self confidence to face the real life situation.

I. I. Theoretical Base of theatrical learning.

This study is an attempt to know the scope of learning through theater, based on the modern theories of learning, intelligence, personality and Educational philosophy.

1.1.1. Multiple Intelligence and the Theater

According to David Wechsler, "Intelligence is the aggregate or global capacity of an individual to act purposefully, to think rationally, and to deal effectively with his environment". Skill of problem solving is considered as a chief characteristic of good intelligence. Theory of Multiplicity of Intelligence put forwarded by Howard Gardner played a significant role in teaching learning process of present educational scenario. While analyzing the Intelligence Gardner identified nine types of intelligence such as, 1. Logical Mathematical intelligence 2. Visual Spatial Intelligence 3. Verbal Linguistic Intelligence 4. Bodily kinesthetic Intelligence 5. Naturalistic intelligence 6. Existentialistic Intelligence 7. Musical Rhythmic Intelligence 8. Intra personal Intelligence and 9. Interpersonal Intelligence. He identified specific areas in the human brain related to specific intelligence. If any damage occurred in these particular areas the person will lose the ability related to that area. He also found that each part of the intelligence can work either isolated or together.

(i) Verbal Linguistic Intelligence

People with high verbal-linguistic intelligence display a facility with words and languages. They are typically good at reading, writing, telling stories and memorizing words and dates. Broca and Wernicke are the parts associated with this intelligence in the brain. Those who are good in linguistic intelligence excel in reception, comprehension and communication of ideas. Theater pedagogy helps in the development of linguistic intelligence as it includes dialogue oriented drama, scriptwriting, converting works from other discourses to drama, drama practice, discussion etc.

(ii) Logical and mathematical intelligence.

It is the capacity to carry out mathematical operations, analyse problems logically and investigate issues scientifically. It also involves the ability to detect patterns and conceptual and abstract thinking. The theatrical method of learning helps to develop the logical and Mathematical intelligence by converting written text to visual text, designing the setting and theatrical effects, making tools, techniques and strategies needed for communication,

(iii) Intra personal intelligence.

It is the ability to understand oneself, appreciate one's own feelings, fears and motivation. People with Intra personal Intelligence are skilled at self-reflection, self-assessment and self-improvement. Self confidence, liberal thinking, personal ideology etc are also the result of this intellect. Drama being a creative medium of performance is the most effective method to develop the Intra personal Intelligence.

(iv) Musical intelligence

The skill to sing, appreciate or learn and retain musical components, rhythm etc are reflections of this intellect. Background music, songs and rhythmic body movements in drama will help to enhance this intelligence.

(v) Inter personal intelligence

This intelligence can be located at the front side of the brain. It helps to understand others' thoughts, emotions, needs and interests in an effective manner and act accordingly. The personality skills like involving in social and group activities, easy social interactions are all reflections of this intellect. As Drama is a group performance of art and games, it will enhance this intelligence and thereby develop one's personality.

(vi) Bodily kinesthetic intelligence

The right hemisphere of the brain controls the left side of the body and the left hemisphere controls the right side of the body. This control over the body movements is actually an intellectual skill. This

intelligence facilitates sports, games, constructive activities, dance, acting etc. This intelligence which is most necessary for the actors has direct relation with drama.

(vii) Visual-Spatial intelligence

It is this intelligence that makes the Pilots, captains, engineers and designers efficient for their profession. This is found in the right hemisphere of the brain. The skill to draw pictures, posters, collage, diagrams, maps, building plans etc are result of this intellect. The theater mode of teaching enhances this intellect when the exit and entrance of the characters, their position on stage, the body movements etc are designed for the execution of drama.

(viii) Naturalistic intelligence

This intelligence helps to know, understand, love and protect nature. It enables one to get easily adapted to the ways of nature and also makes him/her react against anti natural activities. Drama is the best medium to know and communicate the message of nature because nature is one of the strongest themes in drama.

Only when ample opportunities are given to each modalities of intelligence it shows creative developments. With the lack of opportunities they remain idle. And here lies the academic importance of drama because drama is the only medium which enhances all the various intelligence at a time. When holistic development of intelligence is the major objective of a curriculum, drama too should get the deserving space in it. It has been proved that theater training could bring incredible development in the mentally challenged children.

1.1.2 Emotional Quotient-EQ

It was Daniel Goleman who made a study on EQ. He discovered that for most people, EQ is more important than IQ in attaining success in their lives and careers. EQ is the capability of individuals to recognize their own and other people's emotions, discern between their feelings and label them approximately, use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior. Self awareness, self regulation and control, motivation, empathy, ability to make decisions and other social skills also come under this. This intelligence helps an individual to identify his space in the social arena.

It is through discussions and debate a written text is converted to a dramatic script and performance. These debates help to overcome the limitations of stage and performance. The most challenging process in the creation of drama is to make a message communicate to the spectators. When an individual passes through the above mentioned mental process and activities his EQ gets developed.

1.1.3 Social constructivism and Theater

Child centeredness, process orientation, activity baseness are some of the features of constructivist classrooms, it admits the ability of students to construct knowledge as pre skill. In a constructivist classroom the focus of teaching shifts from the teacher to the student. The classroom is no longer a place where the teacher pours knowledge into passive students. Here the students are urged to be actively involved in their own learning- thinking activities and problem solving. In the constructivist Classrooms, both teacher and students think of knowledge as a dynamic, ever changing view of the world we live in and the ability to successfully stretch and explore that view. These classrooms include the following perspectives:

- Students get an opportunity to choose, to plan and to work either in isolation or in group within the limits of curriculum.
- In such a classroom students are able to analyse a problem from different angles and approach it from different perspectives and take rational stand.

observation, rational thinking, analysis, inference and review. They give importance to the cognitive process and accept cognition ability as the basis of man.

A schema according to Piaget is the cognitive structure that is acquired by children by interacting with their physical and social environment. These schemas are constantly in the process of being modified or changed. They are revised and elaborated upon each time the child encounters new experiences. In doing this children create their own understanding of the world, interpret their own experiences and knowledge, and, subsequently use this knowledge to solve more complex problems. The brain is constantly working to build and rebuild itself as it takes in new information through adaptation and accommodation and thereby enhances understanding. Mental constructions are formed by assimilation and accommodation.

The problems that pose challenges create mental disequilibrium in the learner. The child attempts problem solving in order to overcome the internal stress created by this disequilibrium and thus attains equilibrium. Equilibrium is attained as a result of rebuilding the schema through assimilation and accommodation.

The task of converting a text to a drama is a challenge and thus creates mental disequilibrium in the learner. To solve this problem the learner interacts with the surroundings (library, teachers, peers, experts) and assimilates new knowledge elements which when converted become schema through dramatic endeavors. Later this schema is enriched through further discussion and judgments and finally attains equilibrium with the creation and performance of Drama. And thus the learning takes place.

1.1.5 Social constructivism through group learning

Social constructivism is a learning process developed by the observations of Russian Psychologist Lev Vygotsky (1896-1934). Social constructivism points out the role of social and cultural elements in the process of learning. According to him an individual creates and recreates the society and vice versa.

A Social problem creates disequilibrium in the mental framework of a child. He tries to solve this by interacting with himself or the teacher or society. Thus knowledge is constructed. According to Jerome S Bruner there are three levels for problem solving learning:

- I. To create readiness - inspire the learners to do the activity.
2. Maintaining the interest -to creatively maintain the interest up till the activity is completed.
3. Give guidance to act with a goal.

In problem solving method it is the problem that leads to the activity. And it is the role of the teacher to present the problem in an inspiring manner. Problem solving tasks should come from the side of the learner. According to him the following four learning process should be given due care to attain better learning.

1. Preparing to learn
2. Effective selection and arrangement of activities so as to construct knowledge.
3. Well organised presentation.
4. Giving prizes.

Discovery learning, co-operative learning, collaborative learning and debate learning are a few learning processes that come under social constructivism.

1.5.1 Scope of Collaborative learning

The learning process which occurs through the mutual interaction between the learner, the teacher, materials and the content is the most effective learning process. A class room with collaborative learning would definitely provide space for the teacher and the learner to share knowledge. The learners will have a role in planning and executing their own objectives, pedagogy and learning activities. Each group will be a diverse group of students with varied taste and talents. Thus in a collaborative classroom

everyone learns from everyone else and no student is deprived of this opportunity for making contributions and appreciating the contributions of others.

Hence shared knowledge and authority, mediated learning and heterogeneous groups of students are essential characteristics of collaborative classroom. These characteristics necessitate new roles for teachers. A teacher involves in creating rich environments and activities for linking new information to prior knowledge, providing opportunities for collaborative work and problem solving and offering students a multiplicity of authentic learning tasks. Teacher also provides scaffolding at the right time and the right level in order to overcome the difficulties and achieve better learning. Another way that the teacher facilitates collaborative classroom is to establish classroom with diverse and flexible social structures and confirm the learning achievements by giving the feedbacks effectively.

By considering these facts we can see that theater method carries all the process and characteristics of social constructivism, co-operative and collaborative types of learning. In the light of aims and objectives of education and curriculum it is clear that we should give priority to theater pedagogy in all levels of education in general and the education of differently abled in specific.

2. PRACTICE

A revision of the conventional teaching method is necessary to attain the aims and objectives of the higher Education. There should be a change from teacher centered classroom to student centered classroom which will provide space for self learning, meta cognition and analysis and thereby learning and sharing of knowledge.

2.1. Objectives of the study

1. To recognize the effectiveness of curriculum transactions through theater method.
2. To observe the influence of theater mode of learning among the differently abled students.
3. To observe the change effected by the theater mode of teaching in creativity, analysis, content comprehension, self confidence and personality.

2.2 Tools for Data collection

The authenticity of the study depends upon the use of accurate tools and techniques. Moreover structured observation is also used as a technique for data collection. Achievement test is used twice to evaluate the content comprehension, creativity and the skill of analysis. The first test is conducted during the beginning of the Academic year before introducing theater mode of teaching to evaluate the prior knowledge and prerequisite of the students. And the second test was conducted at the end of academic year after the completion of theater mode of teaching. The confidence level of the students was determined by evaluating the collected responses for the statements of 25 behavioral patterns.

The inventory used for the study is prepared by the researcher himself after the reliability and validity were approved by the experts. This inventory was used in the beginning and end of the year as pre-test and post-test to determine the significant difference in the level of confidence. Role play method was used to evaluate the performance of the students. The task was to perform a mime by picking up a lot which the spectators should identify. The performances of the students were video graphed which was later used for evaluation using appropriate indicators. This was also conducted twice a year to evaluate pre-requisites and acquired skills.

Achievement test

A Question Paper containing three sections A, B and C was used for written test. In section A, lines from an unfamiliar poem was given to interpret and identity the metaphors. Part B of the QP is indented to evaluate the creativity of the students. And for this Pulikat Raveendran's poem, "otta" was given by excluding the last line and the students were asked to complete it with their own creativity. Part C is indented to evaluate the content comprehension of the students. For that they were given 6 questions from the 3rd and 4th semester texts which they have already learnt.

5. The average score of 54 in the pretest becomes 83 in the post test. That means within 6 months, theater workshop and the conversion of texts into dramatic performance could bring an average of 29% increase in the self confidence of the students.
6. In the evaluation of personality based on role play also there is distinct differences between the pre and post performances. In the pre test 50% students got B grade and 50% got C and D grade. But the fact that 100% of the students got A grade in the post test proves that theater workshop is one of the best tools to increase the self confidence and improve the body language of the students. The unhealthy responses like fear, anxiety, hesitation, embarrassment, limited body movements, shallow performance and imagination, over consciousness about body, haste, mental stress, shivering, laziness, dropping heads, laughing etc were visible in the pre test. But in contrast to the pre test, post test was rich with qualities like self confidence, lack of inhibitions, facing the audience, least conscious about the body, performance using the whole body, free movement of body by sitting, lying and dancing, focused and concept rich performance, variety and uniqueness in imagination. The notable thing is that the students participated with great interest and enjoyed the whole process.
7. The score achieved by the mentally retarded child, Sharat.p in the pre test conducted to evaluate content comprehension was only 37.5 %. But this has become 75% in the post test. That means a 100 % increase in comprehensive skill. The score of 68% for self confidence in the pre test changed to 80% in the post test. That means an increase of 12%. The score for creativity rose from 0% to 75%. Again, there was a visible hike in the score for interpretation skill from 0% to 70%. This shows that theater mode of transaction can bring incredible changes in such children.
8. The different parts of the brain will remain active only when appropriate chances are provided to each part. With the lack of opportunities these parts will remain idle. Here lies the academic importance of drama. There is no other discourse like drama which will enhance all the intelligence at a time.
9. A text is converted to screenplay and performance through debates and discussion. These debates help to approach and express a text from a dramatic perspective. The most challenging process in the creation of drama is to make a message communicate to the spectators. When an individual passes through the above mentioned activities in a theater workshop his EQ gets developed.
10. All the qualities of a Social constructivist classroom which enables a meaningful learning can also be attained through Theater mode of learning. The characteristics of both these classes are one and the same.
11. The task of converting a text to a drama is a challenge and thus creates mental disequilibrium in the learner. To solve this problem the learner interacts with the surroundings (library, teachers, peers, experts) and assimilates new knowledge elements which he/she then converts to schema through dramatic endeavors. Later this schema is enriched through further discussion and judgments and finally attains equilibrium with the creation of Drama. Thus learning occurs. This educational theory of Piaget also stands closer to theater method.
12. Discovery learning, co-operative learning, Collaborative learning, etc are important learning methods that come under Social constructivist theory of learning. Theater mode of learning constitutes the objectives of all these learning methods.

2.7. Application of findings.

As per the study we can see significant improvement in the skills like content comprehension, creativity, analytical skill and confidence. Thus theater mode of transaction should be given due importance in UG curriculum. At least a three day residential theater workshop should be included in each year of the BA programme as part of curriculum. There should be financial aid from UGC/Collegiate Education for conducting the camp. In order to conduct theater mode of transactions teachers should be given theater skills through orientation and refresher courses. Special Theater workshop related with curriculum objectives may be given exclusively to differently abled students of different colleges under the

University. This module should be prepared by Theater artists, teachers and experts through state level workshop.

Websites or blogs containing drama, scripts and videos related to curriculum should be introduced under Collegiate Education or universities. A panel of researchers, experts, and theater artists should be made available in these sites. Theater Clubs should be given due importance in colleges. Sangeeta Nataka Academy should encourage the theater Clubs of colleges by providing opportunities to present and watch dramas. International Campus theater fest should be conducted by Academy to provide opportunities for local, National and International plays. A state level journal with Drama Scripts and theater news should be introduced. A weightage should be given for PG admission to those who participate in social awareness plays.

Conclusion

Apart from a popular, cultural entertainment discourse, this study reveals theater as an effective tool in the field of teaching-learning process. Theater can be seen as a unique tool to achieve almost all the aims and objectives of Education. The pedagogic importance lies in the process undergone by the students in between the text and final performance.

The modern theories in psychology, educational philosophy and neurology underline the educational importance of Theater method. The study proves that theater mode has a greater influence in the differently abled students compared to normal students. Study also shows that theater mode of Curriculum transaction makes authentic development in the fields of content comprehension, creativity, analytical skill and confidence.

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